

PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL RELATIONS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: *This article discusses the system of preparing future teachers for professional pedagogical relations as a result of many years of experience in working with students in a purposeful manner.*

Keywords: *communication, communicative, student, persuasion, attitude, teacher, professional and pedagogical relations.*

As a result of many years of experience in working with students, the following system of preparation of future teachers for professional pedagogical relations has emerged:

I. The first stage.

1. Causation Organizational Interview:

A) instructions for the future profession;

B) an explanation of the causes, goals and objectives of a socio-personal nature;

C) organization of the intended results;

2. Study of basic theoretical and practical knowledge of professional and pedagogical relations of students:

A) generalization and analysis of knowledge;

B) to convey the results of the analysis of the requirements, focusing on the level of knowledge in the field of professional and pedagogical relations, the initial, insufficient;

II. The main stage.

1. Indicate a set of topics and issues that need to be studied.

2. Mastering the basic theoretical foundations of professional and pedagogical relations.

A) To consider communicative activity in pedagogical practice as an important value of education;

B) To determine the role and importance of professional-pedagogical relations in the communicative and pedagogical activities of students;

V) Review of the concept of "professional-pedagogical (role of relations) relations", tasks, features, types and forms, methods of pedagogical relations, its art, the size, indicators of this relationship, the requirements for it ;

3. Professional-pedagogical relations of students and practical aspects of mutual generations.

- The basics of pedagogical relations;
- pedagogical goals and impacts;
- preparation for this relationship, goals and objectives;
- The process of pedagogical relations, itself, its technology;
- pedagogical approach to their options, technologies, various tasks, their independent, professional and pedagogical implementation (solution);
- consider the requirements for the student and the teacher in the process of this relationship;

III. The next stage.

Students - theoretical and practical training of future teachers.

1. Preparation of reports, reports, abstracts.
2. Writing pedagogical essays, essays.
3. Develop scenarios of measures to address the communicative problems of lessons with an emphasis on pedagogical approach.
4. Discuss the features, types, manifestations and forms of pedagogical relations.
 - The content and themes of dialogues and debates (for students);
 - Communicative-pedagogical situation, in particular, pedagogical-professional relations;
5. Selection of pedagogical actions and favorable pedagogical attitudes in different situations;
6. Carrying out theoretical and practical tests on professional and pedagogical relations;
7. Development, compilation and memorization of advice, notes, recommendations on professional and pedagogical relations;
8. Work on speech, pronunciation, means of non-verbal communication (trainings);
9. Discuss the role of behavior, walking, dressing, etc. in a teacher's communicative activity.

IV. The final stage.

1. Compare, summarize, and analyze the results with the baseline data.
2. Conclusion.
3. Development of proposals and recommendations for improving knowledge in the field of general and professional-pedagogical relations.

V. Self-assessment of the future teacher as a result of practical observation of professional-pedagogical relations (during pedagogical practice).

Experiments have shown that the requirements for future teachers in the system of expression of such theoretical material in professional-pedagogical relations, its intellectual, theoretical and practical use, including in a real pedagogical situation in a specific professional environment.

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